

Title: Working landscapes under climate change need to be green, moist and cool - a case study of Germany

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Keypoints

- Vegetation greenness is the dominant driver of cooling, exerting stronger influence on land surface temperature (LST)
- Forests and wetlands provide effective thermal buffering, while urban and agricultural areas act as thermal hotspots
- “Green–moist–cool” emerges as core ecological triad linking thermal regulation, moisture availability, and ecosystem functioning

Abstract

Urban heat has captured public attention, yet broader “heat landscapes” remain less widely recognized, and the extent to which land surface temperature (LST) reflects ecosystem working capacity is less emphasized at national scales. Using Landsat LST from hot days and end-of-summer vegetation greenness, we mapped thermal hotspots and functional landscapes across Germany and analyzed drivers of thermal performance with correlation analyses and mixed-effects models. The results provide evidence that thermal regulation, vegetation cover, and moisture availability are tightly coupled, supporting “green–moist–cool” as a fundamental ecological triad sustaining working landscapes. Late-summer vegetation greenness emerged as the dominant predictor of lower LST, exerting a stronger cooling influence than precipitation or altitude. Land cover explains ~17% of LST variance, with forests particularly effective at cooling, whereas built-up areas and agriculture contribute to elevated LST. Vegetation greenness was the strongest predictor of rainfall (+297 mm per unit increase). LST has a strong negative effect (−4.05 mm per °C). Reforestation, regreening, and wetland restoration increase vegetation cover, which enhances energy capture (via photosynthesis), moisture, carbon sequestration, and nutrient cycling. They also improve landscape connectivity and thermal buffering, stabilizing microclimates and increasing the system’s ability to dissipate energy gradients — key aspects of thermodynamic work capacity. We recommend using a Green-Moist-Cool Index to monitor ecosystem functionality. This enables the quantification of progress in sustainable land development and the identification of priority areas for restoration and natural climate protection.

Plain language summary

We studied how hot different parts of Germany are, not just cities. Using satellite data, we compared how hot the land gets on very warm days with how green it is at the end of summer. We found a clear pattern: Green, moist and cool conditions go well together. Places with more vegetation are cooler than can be explained by rainfall or elevation. Land cover is responsible for around 17% of the temperature differences. Forests are usually cooler than built-up areas and farmland without trees and shrubs. Places that are greener and cooler also tend to receive more rainfall. This helps us to focus our efforts on restoration and adaptation to climate change. Regular satellite monitoring can track the health of landscapes and help us to make better decisions about how we use the land, particularly in the context of climate change.

1. Introduction

Cities with limited vegetation are known to heat up rapidly during hot periods, increasing health risks for residents under climate change. This phenomenon, widely studied as the urban heat island effect, has received considerable research and policy attention (Connors et al., 2013; Eneche et al., 2024; Şahin et al., 2025). However, far less attention has been paid to the existence of wider *heat landscapes*, non-urban areas that also experience elevated land surface temperatures (LST) due to vegetation loss, land degradation, and intensive land use (Ali et al., 2025; P. Liu et al., 2024; Xiao et al., 2022). These landscapes not only have a temperature problem but are also generally less functional. While they sometimes provide agricultural products or human infrastructure, they contribute to human wellbeing in a one-sided way at best and may even pose risks to it. In any case, these are extremely vulnerable landscapes.

Many studies have shown that vegetation helps to regulate surface temperature. Greener, more vegetated landscapes tend to be cooler, as vegetation cools surfaces through evapotranspiration and shading (Guha & Govil, 2021; Hussain et al., 2023; Jouy et al., 2025; Tariq et al., 2019). The structure and type of land cover also influence the degree of temperature regulation; forests and wetlands, for example, can buffer extreme heat more effectively than agricultural or built-up areas (Gohr et al., 2021; Njoku & Tenenbaum, 2022). Additionally, there is a rapidly growing body of evidence highlighting the importance of vegetation for human wellbeing, particularly regarding mental and physical health. Forests in particular have been the focus of attention, with a wide range of positive effects being described (e.g., Gillerot et al., 2025).

Vegetation and land use also play a key role in hydrological regimes, including groundwater renewal and the quality of drinking water reservoirs, as well as regulating surface runoff (e.g., Ficklin et al., 2024). Climate change is altering recharge patterns, resulting in significant changes to the seasonal distribution of snowmelt in many regions. This affects the timing and quantity of groundwater renewal (Riedel & Weber, 2020). Changes in land use can significantly impact recharge rates. In some cases, this impact is greater than that of climate change alone. Examples of such changes include deforestation, urbanization, and irrigation (Riedel et al., 2023; Riedel & Weber, 2020). It is particularly well documented in arid and semi-arid regions that areas with sparse vegetation have higher LSTs. This is because there is reduced shading and less evapotranspiration, meaning more solar energy is absorbed directly by bare soil and transformed into heat (Abera et al., 2018; Olmos-Trujillo et al., 2020). Deforestation and loss of plant cover can increase local temperatures, especially during dry

periods when there is less vegetation to dissipate radiation energy and store heat (e.g., Adepoju et al., 2019; Spracklen et al., 2018). In dry regions, the decline in moisture recycling by vegetation in dry years has been shown to provide a positive feedback that intensifies dry conditions (Miralles et al., 2016).

Vegetation even contributes to local rainfall through evapotranspiration, which recycles moisture back into the atmosphere. Losing vegetation reduces this process, resulting in less rainfall (Miralles et al., 2016; Spracklen et al., 2018). Conversely, restoring vegetation can lead to increased rainfall (Zhang et al., 2021). There is now clear evidence that high LST negatively affect precipitation. Explanations provided by Sun & Wang (2022) suggest that a large saturation deficit reduces the intensity of precipitation by slowing the rate at which convective updrafts condense and accelerating the evaporation of condensate. The suppression of precipitation induced by heat would be one of several mechanisms causing drought and heatwaves to co-occur and potentially self-propagate, triggered by both mean and extreme temperature values. Schumacher et al. (2022) found that dryland droughts are particularly likely to self-propagate because evaporation tends to respond strongly to increased soil water stress, and that in dry landscapes, there is a demonstrable decline in precipitation levels. Multiple studies show a robust negative correlation between rising LSTs and cloud cover. As surface temperatures increase, cloud coverage—especially low and mid-level clouds—tends to decrease over land (Liu et al., 2023; Mendoza et al., 2021; Stauffer & Wing, 2022). Regardless of whether cloud cover is accompanied by precipitation, it cools the land surface by filtering solar radiation. Field studies confirm that reduced cloudiness increases light and temperature, which can decrease water use efficiency and net carbon uptake in many ecosystems, especially during dry periods (Carbone et al., 2013; Fischer et al., 2009; Williams et al., 2018).

While these relationships have not yet been studied in all biomes, it is clear that land and ecosystem characteristics significantly influence energy uptake and conversion, which in turn are strongly interlinked to hydrological processes and vegetation productivity. In the context of climate change and rising energy input, the importance of the corresponding regulating functions of ecosystems is inherently increasing.

In this context, we advance the concept of *working landscapes* by reframing it through the lens of systems ecology. While the term has traditionally referred to areas managed for 'direct' economic production, such as agriculture or forestry, we propose a broader definition that emphasizes ecological functionality. Specifically, we define working landscapes as ecosystems

that perform work, in the sense of thermodynamics, by capturing, transforming, and storing energy and matter through ecological processes. This include the accumulation of biomass through three-dimensional vegetation structure, the regulation of microclimates via evapotranspiration and shading, the retention and cycling of water and nutrients, and the provision of habitats for biodiversity (Ruijsch et al., 2024; van der Vliet et al., 2024).

Under this definition, working landscapes play a critical role in maintaining or enhancing the resilience of socioecological systems, particularly to climatic stressors. This study emphasizes socioecological resilience because working landscapes are coupled human–natural systems, human decisions (governance, land use, economies) shape ecosystem processes, and ecological change feeds back onto livelihoods and behavior. Therefore, resilience is treated as socioecological: it concerns two-way feedbacks and the adaptive capacity of both social and biophysical components (Adger, 2000; Folke et al., 2002, 2016). The concept of working landscapes is fundamental to establishing a livable planet, as defined by the World Bank. This definition encompasses a planet that is capable of supporting environmental health, in conjunction with investments in human and physical capital, thereby aiming to enhance the quality of life, livelihoods and living standards for all individuals (Damania et al., 2025).

The state of ecosystems and their capacity to perform physical work are strategically important for all regions and countries. Despite this, little work has been done to map and evaluate (dys)functional landscapes at large spatial - or national - scales or to integrate such data into land-use or restoration planning. In this study, we take the Federal Republic of Germany as a case study, an industrialized, densely populated country with significant anthropogenic changes to its ecosystems. Substantial areas are characterized by agriculture, urban systems and infrastructure.

From 2018 onwards, Germany was hard hit by an extreme compound, multi-year heat and drought event that set a new benchmark for Europe (Rakovec et al., 2022). Forests are intensively managed to varying degrees; in recent years, the occurrence of extreme weather events such as heatwaves and prolonged drought has led to substantial forest dieback on a large scale (Knapp et al., 2024). Although located in a temperate biome, heat and water shortages are increasingly being recognized as relevant health policy challenges (Frasch et al., 2025; Mücke & Litvinovitch, 2020; Winklmayr et al., 2022) and economic risks across many relevant sectors such as agriculture, energy or transport (Ademmer et al., 2023; Chauvet et al., 2025; Golub et al., 2022; Schmitt et al., 2022). The hot and dry summer of 2018 alone led to

unprecedented social, ecological and economic consequences (Xoplaki et al., 2025). Vegetation changes triggered by climate change, such as forest dieback, can lead to further socioeconomic risks, including decreased drinking water quality (Winter et al., 2025).

Despite the theoretical and empirical foundations supporting this concept, there is no standardized approach to identify and monitor such landscapes across national scales. However, satellite remote sensing now offers the opportunity to systematically and spatially explicitly map thermal behavior and vegetation function (van der Vliet et al., 2024; Xiao et al., 2022). This study aims to develop a spatial framework for identifying and assessing *working landscapes* in Germany using satellite data. We use LST and vegetation greenness (NDVI) as proxies for regulating functions and work capacity of ecosystems. Specifically, we aim to:

1. map the spatial distribution of both thermal landscapes and relatively functional green ecosystems and hereby provide information to orient national restoration, risk reduction, and climate adaptation strategies
2. determine the relationship, if any, between LSTs, land cover, vegetation properties and other parameters, and
3. to propose an evaluative metric for the comparative analysis of landscapes, with the objective of assessing their regulating capacities and functionality in relation to vegetation and temperature, as well as water availability.

2. Methodology and material

2.1.Data

We have used available and appropriate datasets that provided information on greenness, and thus productivity and structure of vegetation; land surface temperatures (LSTs) of different land use types; and the distribution of precipitation as the most important input for moisture (Table S1). Leaf Area Index (LAI) and Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) were considered but, being NDVI-derived and highly collinear with NDVI, were omitted from the models; their relationships are shown in Figure S1. We deliberately chose the years after 2018, which included the five warmest and driest summers in Germany since the beginning of meteorological records.

The data used in this study was extracted through the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform (Google, 2025) which provides cloud-based access to extensive geospatial datasets. These datasets include a range of environmental factors such as LST from Landsat 8 & 9, Normalized

Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS), and other factors like annual precipitation, altitude, land type classification, and tree cover loss.

Although satellite data is becoming more accurate and new datasets with higher spatial and temporal resolution are becoming available, some sources of error and inaccuracy remain. We have taken several steps to minimize the impact of these effects. Additionally, certain irresolvable circumstances must be considered when interpreting the results.

- 2.1.1. **Missing Landsat LST Data:** A major source of error in the dataset was missing Landsat LST data in some areas, which together covered an area of 1400 sq. km (0.4% of Germany). To mitigate this, MODIS LST (NASA, 2021) was used as a replacement, after identifying the same dates and times. However, MODIS LST tends to show lower temperatures (by 2 to 4°C) than Landsat-derived data. This potential underestimation of maximum LST is an inherent limitation of using MODIS data as a substitute. This discrepancy arises primarily from MODIS's coarser spatial resolution (1 km) relative to Landsat (30 m), which causes mixed-pixel averaging across heterogeneous landscapes. Consequently, fine-scale thermal heterogeneity, such as localized urban heat islands, small water bodies, or agricultural fields, is smoothed out, reducing the apparent maximum temperatures (Simó et al., 2016; Vlassova et al., 2014). Therefore, maximum LST in this region is likely underestimated, and this limitation should be considered when interpreting our findings.
- 2.1.2. **Underestimation of daily maximum LST:** Landsat acquires LST data at about 10:15 a.m. (USGS, 2024) and MODIS at 10:30 a.m. (NASA, 2021). Both pass well before the diurnal maximum, as LST usually peaks after midday (12:00–3:00 p.m.), when solar radiation is strongest. Consequently, our estimates underestimate the true maximum LST, and this limitation should be considered when interpreting the results. Still, we expect that the detected spatial patterns of thermal landscapes would not vary greatly if we were able to consider afternoon temperatures.
- 2.1.3. **Cloud Coverage:** Cloud cover frequently affected the availability of LST data from Landsat imagery. Cloud cover often results in missing or unreliable data, particularly over large regions. To address this, we used cloud-filtered datasets to ensure that only reliable temperature values were included in the analysis. The cloud

filtering process minimizes the potential bias introduced by cloud cover, but it remains an important consideration when interpreting the results because the filtering may not completely eliminate all cloud-related artifacts.

2.2. Thermal landscape classification

Particularly, prominent thermal landscapes of Germany were classified based on relatively large continuous patches of hot and cold regions derived from the mean land surface temperature (LST) during hot days (2018–2024). In our study we defined a hot day as one where the maximum LST reached or exceeded 40°C in any pixel in Germany. This classification process involved identifying areas with consistently high and low temperatures to define distinct thermal landscapes across the country. The names given to the identified landscapes were based on the map of German landscapes (BKG, 2019) with several landscapes being combined in some cases. They do not represent administrative units, and the names do not necessarily reflect all the landscapes they contain.

2.3. Landscape greenness

To assess greenness, we use the average Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) values measured in September, hereafter, $NDVI_{sep}$, representing the end of the vegetation period. The greenness data for this month shows the most resistant or functional vegetation. Depending on their health, forests may have lost some of their greenness due to stress caused by summer heat and drought, but they have not yet begun to shed their leaves due to low light levels or low temperatures. In agricultural areas, most crops have been harvested, which frequently exposes the soil, especially when no cover crops are sown. Thus, low $NDVI_{sep}$ reflects (at least temporarily) reduced productivity, evapotranspiration, and poor ground cover. Likewise, dry pastures and other grasslands typically lose greenness as grasses desiccate and brown. $NDVI_{sep}$ provides a conservative, comparable reference to residual vegetative activity across land-cover types and minimizes seasonal biases.

2.4. Statistical analysis

The statistical analysis was performed using R version 4.3.3, employing linear mixed-effects models (Table S2) to assess the relationships between land surface temperature (LST), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index ($NDVI_{sep}$), canopy height, precipitation, and altitude. Spearman's correlation indicated a moderate association between $NDVI_{sep}$ and canopy height

($\rho = 0.54$). Collinearity was assessed via variance-inflation factors (VIF; `performance::check_collinearity`); all fixed-effect VIFs were < 5 , indicating acceptable collinearity. Consistent with general regression theory, LMMs are robust to mild–moderate correlations among predictors (here, $\rho = 0.54$), coefficients remain generally unbiased while standard errors may increase; even strong collinearity mainly reduces precision rather than inducing bias (Schielzeth et al., 2020). We also estimated reciprocal specifications with LST and precipitation as alternating outcomes to assess robustness to outcome choice and to express effect sizes in dual units ($^{\circ}\text{C}$ per mm; mm per $^{\circ}\text{C}$), interpreting all coefficients as covariate-adjusted (non-causal) associations. The models included fixed effects such as NDVI_{sep} , canopy height, precipitation, altitude, and year, while accounting for random effects associated with land type to explain spatial variability across different land categories. Additionally, we tested for regional differences in the Green-Moist-Cool Index (GMCI) using a Kruskal–Wallis rank-sum test. Post-hoc Wilcoxon rank-sum tests with a Benjamini–Hochberg False Discovery Rate (FDR) adjustment were then used to identify which region pairs differed.

2.5.Green-Moist-Cool Index

We devised a Green-Moist-Cool Index (GMCI) at the pixel level that reflects the triad of ecosystem functionality and the conditions for this impacted by climate change, which is characterized by rising temperatures, more frequent and severe droughts, and damage to vegetation. Our novel index to summarize the combined patterns of LST, NDVI_{sep} , and precipitation. For each year (2018–2024), NDVI_{sep} at the end of the vegetation period and precipitation were linearly scaled to a common 0–1 range so that larger values reflect greener and moister conditions. Federal States and prominent thermal landscapes were ranked based on the GMCI. As water generally has a very low NDVI and would therefore be poorly represented in a green–moist–cool metric, we identified the pixels representing water bodies and computed the GMCI from only the precipitation and LST components in these areas.

Land surface temperature (LST) was scaled to 0–1 and then inverted so that cooler areas score higher. The GMCI for each pixel is the simple average of these three rescaled layers. Annual GMCI maps were then averaged to produce a multi-year composite. Higher GMCI scores (approaching 1) indicate greener, moister, and cooler environments, while lower scores (approaching 0) signal hot, dry, and sparsely vegetated states. We used these composite scores to rank thermal landscape units by their capacity to buffer heat.

3. Results

3.1. Land surface temperatures

3.1.1. Mean thermal patterns and classification of landscapes

The multi-year composite of hot-day LST (2018–2024) (Fig. 1, Table S3) highlights persistent thermal contrasts across Germany. While interannual climatic variation modulates the severity of heat exposure, the geography of heat hotspots and relatively cool regions is remarkably stable.

Fig. 1. Mean land surface temperature (LST) on hot days in Germany (2018–2024) illustrating the spatial distribution of mean LST on hot days, defined as days on which at least one pixel in Germany reached or exceeded 40 °C—derived from cloud-filtered Landsat 8 and 9 imagery at

30 m resolution. The central map displays the multi-year composite average of hot-day LSTs across the entire period. Red tones indicate areas with consistently higher surface temperatures, while blue tones reflect cooler regions.

Based on LST patterns from 2018–2024, we identified 32 prominent thermal landscapes (Fig. 2) that consistently proved to be either above-average warm or cool. Table S4 and Table S5 show mean LST of hot days for the thermal landscapes and the federal states of Germany.

Thermal landscapes differed significantly in mean LST across Germany and included intensively used lowland agricultural and peri-urban regions led by Vorderpfalz–Rhein-Main (32.8 °C), followed by Maifeld–Neuwieder Becken, München, Stuttgart–Nordbaden, and the peri-urban belts of Köln–Niederrhein–Münsterland and Teltow–Berlin–Barnim; additional high-range landscapes included Oderbruch, Altmark–Leipzig–Thüringer Basin, Emsland–Oldenburg–Hannover, Breisgau, Mittelfranken, Prignitz, Uckermark, Warnow–Vorpommern, and Nordfriesland. In contrast, cooling landscapes clustered in upland and forested regions, with the coolest conditions at Bodensee (23.7°C), followed by the Alpen, Bayerischer Wald, Erzgebirge, Solling–Reinhardswald, Oberallgäu, Hohes Venn–Rureifel, Thüringer Wald, Müritz–Schorfheide, Pfälzerwald, Schwarzwald, Soonwald–Taunus, Hochsauerland, and Odenwald–Spessart.

There are certainly other landscapes that could be defined and named. Comparatively cooler landscapes, for example, include parts of the Eifel, the Swabian Alb and the Alpine foothills.

Fig. 2. National classification of thermal landscapes in Germany based on mean land surface temperature (LST) of hot days from 2018 to 2024. Hot days were defined as days on which at least one pixel reached or exceeded 40 °C, derived from cloud-filtered Landsat 8 and 9 imagery at 30 m resolution. Red tones indicate hotspots, while blue tones indicate cooler regions.

3.1.2. Interannual variation in hot-day LST

Hot-day land surface temperature (LST) varied strongly across Germany between 2018 and 2024 both in intensity and spatial extent (Fig. 1). The number of hot days ranged from a

maximum of 70 days in 2018 to a minimum of 25 days in 2021, reflecting pronounced interannual climatic variability. Years such as 2018 and 2022 were characterized by widespread thermal anomalies, with elevated LST across most lowland regions. In contrast, 2020 and 2021 showed markedly cooler conditions, particularly in forested and mountainous areas. Intermediate years (2019, 2023, 2024) exhibited mixed patterns, combining localized hotspots with widespread cooling in uplands.

Throughout all years, the upland forested landscapes of southern and central Germany (e.g., Harz, Thuringian Forest, Bavarian Forest, Black Forest, and the Alps) consistently acted as thermal refugia, experiencing cooler surface temperatures relative to surrounding lowlands. However, even within these areas, the degree of cooling fluctuated, showing reduced buffering capacity during extreme summers (e.g., 2018, 2022) and stronger cooling in milder years (e.g., 2020, 2021). In contrast, agricultural plains, river valleys, and peri-urban landscapes repeatedly exhibited higher LST, with the spatial footprint of hotspots expanding during dry and hot years.

3.2. Vegetation greenness

Annual NDVI_{sep} maps (Fig. 3) show overall stable spatial patterns of vegetation greenness across Germany with notable interannual variation. NDVI_{sep} was moderate in 2018 and increased in 2019, particularly in northern lowlands and forested uplands. A clear decline occurred in 2020, most evident in eastern lowlands (Oderbruch, Altmark-Leipzig-Thüringer Basin, Uckermark) and in parts of western lowlands (Köln–Niederrhein–Münsterland). Greenness rebounded in 2021, especially across southern uplands (Black Forest, Bavarian Forest, Alps), but declined again in 2022, showing the lowest values in lowland agricultural landscapes such as Prignitz and Teltow-Berlin-Barnim. NDVI_{sep} increased again in 2023, while 2024 experienced conditions close to the long-term mean.

The multi-year average (Fig. 3) highlights consistently high NDVI_{sep} in forested uplands (e.g., Bavarian Forest, Alps, Black Forest) and lower values in eastern and central lowlands. The time series (Fig. S2) further indicates that many forests maintained stable greenness, while lowland landscapes exhibited marked declines in 2020 and 2022, followed by partial recovery. However, some forest regions experienced substantial 'browning', such as the Harz Mountains, where there was significant dieback of Norway spruce, as well as intensive salvage logging.

The NDVI_{sep} time series (Fig. S2) shows consistently higher values for forests (0.75–0.82) compared to agricultural areas (0.55–0.70). Forest NDVI_{sep} remained relatively stable with

This manuscript has been submitted to [Earth's Future](#) for consideration.

minor fluctuations, while agricultural NDVI_{sep} varied more strongly across years. Peak NDVI_{sep} values occurred in 2021 and 2023 for all land-use types, whereas lower values were observed in 2020 and 2022.

Fig. 3. Late vegetation period Normalized Difference Vegetation Index ($NDVI_{sep}$) in Germany (2018–2024). The maps illustrate $NDVI_{sep}$ values for September (late growing season) from

2018 to 2024, based on MODIS. The central map shows the mean NDVI_{sep} across all years. The visualization highlights spatial and temporal patterns in vegetation cover across Germany.

3.3.Precipitation

Precipitation showed strong spatial contrasts across Germany (Figs. 5). Eastern and northeastern lowlands (Oderbruch, Altmark, Uckermark, Lusatia) with a more continental climate consistently recorded the lowest values (< 600–800 mm), while western uplands and the Bavarian Alps received the highest amounts (> 2,000 mm, locally > 3,000 mm). Dry years included 2018, 2019, and 2022, with substantial deficits concentrated in the east, whereas 2021 and 2023 were markedly wetter across most regions.

The mean pattern (Fig. 4) shows persistent east–west and north-south gradients: dry lowlands in the east and northeast, intermediate precipitation in central basins (800–1,200 mm), and wet conditions in western highlands and the Alps (> 2,000 mm).

Fig. 4. Annual precipitation maps (2018–2024). The maps depict spatial patterns of total annual precipitation (in mm) across Germany from 2018 to 2024, based on $1\text{ km} \times 1\text{ km}$ gridded datasets provided by the German Weather Service (DWD). The data were derived through

interpolation of observations from DWD and partner stations, using a digital elevation model and validated via cross-validation with a 17% mean error margin (Maier & Müller-Westermeier, 2010). Red areas indicate drier conditions, while blue areas denote higher precipitation totals.

3.4. Statistical analyses of LST and precipitation model

3.4.1 Biophysical drivers of land surface temperature (LST)

The mixed-effects model i (Table S6) demonstrated that $NDVI_{sep}$ was by far the strongest predictor of LST, exerting a consistent cooling association of -1.97 °C per unit increase. This coefficient was larger than other predictors, underlining the critical role of vegetation greenness in regulating surface temperature. Canopy height provided an additional though smaller buffering association (-0.14 °C per meter), reflecting the contribution of forest structure to local cooling. Altitude and precipitation exhibited weaker but statistically detectable cooling relationships, consistent with adiabatic lapse rate effects and moisture-related evaporative cooling, respectively.

Year-to-year variability was substantial: relative to the 2018 baseline, 2019 was hotter, 2020 and 2021 were markedly cooler, while 2022–2024 were intermediate. These year effects reflect broader climatic anomalies during the study period.

The random effect of land type accounted for 17% of the variance ($ICC = 0.17$), suggesting that categorical differences in land-use/cover contributed additional variability beyond biophysical predictors. Fixed effects alone explained 33.1% of variance (marginal R^2), but inclusion of land type random effects increased explanatory power to 44.4% (conditional R^2).

3.4.2. Vegetation–climate association in precipitation

The mixed-effects model ii (Table S7) showed that $NDVI_{sep}$ was also the strongest positive predictor of rainfall (+297 mm per unit increase), highlighting vegetation's role in promoting evapotranspiration and moisture recycling. In contrast, LST exerted a strong negative association (-4.05 mm per °C), indicating that hotter conditions are associated with suppressed precipitation.

Year effects captured large fluctuations: 2021 was anomalously wet (+172 mm relative to 2018), while 2022 was markedly dry (+71 mm). These anomalies align with known regional climatic extremes during those years.

The random effect of land type explained only 4% of variance ($ICC = 0.04$), indicating that spatial heterogeneity in precipitation is dominated by continuous predictors (vegetation, temperature, altitude) rather than categorical land type differences. Fixed effects explained 58.9% of variance (marginal R^2), increasing marginally to 60.7% with random effects (conditional R^2).

3.4.3. Drivers of LST

The landscape-augmented model (Table S8) reaffirmed $NDVI_{sep}$ as the primary cooling predictor, while also demonstrating clear differences between thermal landscapes. Compared with the Alpine reference landscape, lowland and urban–agricultural regions exhibited systematically higher LST, whereas forest-dominated and high-altitude landscapes tended to be cooler. This reinforces the combined importance of vegetation cover and landscape setting in modulating local climate.

Year effects remained significant, consistent with interannual climate anomalies. Importantly, the random effect of land type explained 27% of the variance ($ICC = 0.27$), more than in the purely biophysical model, indicating that landscape identity captures a substantial share of unexplained variability. Fixed effects explained 27.1% of variance, rising sharply to 46.5% with random effects included, reflecting the efficiency of categorical landscape terms in improving model performance.

3.4.4. Drivers of Precipitation

The precipitation landscape model (Table S9) showed that $NDVI_{sep}$ exhibited the strongest positive association with rainfall, followed by altitude. LST again exerted a suppressing effect, i.e., rainfall decreases as LST increases. Thermal landscapes structured precipitation patterns; however, Alpine regions exhibited systematically higher rainfall.

However, the random effect of land type accounted for only ~1% of the variance, highlighting that most variability in precipitation was explained by vegetation and topography rather than categorical land type. The model performed very strongly, with 85.3% variance explained by

fixed effects (marginal R^2) and only a marginal increase to 85.5% when random effects were included (conditional R^2). The effect of continentality (distance from coastlines) and the prevailing origin of clouds were not taken into account.

3.4.5. Thermal landscape ranking

The Kruskal–Wallis test indicated strong differences in GMCI among regions ($H = 1,798,913$, $df = 31$, $p < 0.001$), with a large effect ($\epsilon^2 \approx 0.51$). Benjamini-Hochberg adjusted post-hoc tests showed that 494 of 496 region pairs differed significantly. The only non-significant contrasts were Breisgau vs. Untere Oder and Uckermark vs. Oderbruch. The boxplot (Fig. 5) shows the distribution of the GMCI for each German state, ordered left-to-right from the lowest to highest median. The dashed horizontal line marks the national median (~ 0.46). At the lower end, lowland and agriculture-dominated regions emerged as areas of concern. Oderbruch and Uckermark formed the lowest (~ 0.37) statistically indistinguishable tier, followed by Maifeld–Neuwieder Becken, Vorderpfalz–Rhein–Main, Altmark–Leipzig–Thüringer Becken, and Teltow–Berlin–Barnim, Warnow–Vorpommern, and Prignitz. Their median GMCI values lie in between ~ 0.37 to ~ 0.41 .

Mittelfranken, Stuttgart–Nordbaden, Köln–Niederrhein–Münsterland, and München clustered within the ~ 0.42 – ~ 0.45 . Emsland–Oldenburg–Hannover (~ 0.45) lay just below the national average; whereas, Breisgau (~ 0.47) and Untere Oder (~ 0.48) were slightly above it. In contrast, forested uplands and alpine areas provided the strongest natural buffering. Median GMCI values clustered within ~ 0.54 – 0.57 , with Pfälzerwald, Thüringer Wald, Erzgebirge, Solling–Reinhardswald, and Hohes Venn–Rureifel (in increasing order). The highest medians occurred in Bodensee (0.70), Germany's largest lake, as well as in the southern mountain regions Oberallgäu (0.68), Alpen (0.66), Schwarzwald (0.61), and Bayerischer Wald (0.59).

Fig. 5. Green-Cool-Moist Index (GMCI) of the prominent thermal landscapes of Germany. The GMCI integrates land surface temperature (LST), September NDVI, and precipitation into a single 0–1 scale, with higher values indicating cooler, greener, and moister conditions.

3.4.6. Temporal variability of LST across different ecosystems and land cover types

Between 2018 and 2024, national LST across land types showed a common temporal cycle, with peaks in 2019 and 2022, a trough in 2021, and relative stabilization thereafter (Fig. 5). Forests were consistently the coolest environments (~27–28 °C), with broadleaf, coniferous, and mixed stands all following the same trajectory and differing only slightly from one another (less than 1 °C). In contrast, open landscapes were considerably warmer and more variable. Vineyards exhibited the highest peaks among natural land types (~30–36 °C), followed by arable land and fruit tree plantations, which showed similar values, while pastures remained mostly ~1 °C cooler than arable land and fruit trees. Among urban-related categories, the hottest land type was industrial sites (~34–35 °C), followed closely by ports and airports, and then military areas. Urban green areas had the lowest LST among urban land uses; however, they showed an increasing trend after 2020. Overall, the results highlight a clear land-use hierarchy: forests consistently buffered heat and remained the coolest, urban areas represented

the hottest environments, and agricultural land occupied an intermediate position but often trended closer to urban than to forest conditions.

The time-series analysis of LST (2018–2024) across German landscapes also shows a clear land-use hierarchy just like the national LST trend: urban areas remain the hottest, forests the coolest, and agriculture lies in between, though often behaving more like urban areas than natural systems (Fig. S4). While there is no uniform rising trend across the years, distinct yearly fluctuations emerge. The year 2019 was notably hot in most regions, followed by a sharp temperature decline in 2020, which stands out as the coolest year across all land uses and landscapes. This cooling event is especially visible in agriculture and urban areas, while forests show only a modest drop, underlining their thermal stability. From 2021 onward, temperatures gradually increased again, with 2022 and 2024 emerging as new peaks. Interestingly, in lowland basins such as Oderbruch and Altmark–Leipzig–Thüringer Becken, agriculture and urban LST values nearly converge, suggesting that croplands heat up almost as much as cities. By contrast, in higher-elevation landscapes like the Alps, Harz, and Erzgebirge, forests maintain a stronger cooling advantage, with a consistent gap of 5–7 °C below urban areas. An interesting observation is the parallel movement of agriculture and urban curves, with both showing sharp rises and falls, while forests act as a stabilizing background, resisting extremes (Fig. S4).

Fig. 6: Composite “Green-Moist-Cool Index” (GMCI) 2018-2024. Higher values indicate greener, moister, cooler conditions. The GMCI integrates land surface temperature (LST),

September NDVI (NDVI_{sep}), and precipitation into a single 0–1 scale, with higher values indicating cooler, greener, and moister conditions.

The map shows the GMCI (Fig. 6) across Germany, highlighting low values in eastern lowlands and peri-urban basins and high values in forested and Alpine regions. The Kruskal–Wallis test indicated strong differences in GMCI among German states ($H = 1,405,803$, $df = 15$, $p < 0.001$), with a moderate effect ($\varepsilon^2 \approx 0.16$). Benjamini-Hochberg adjusted post-hoc tests showed that 120 of 120 state pairs differed significantly. The boxplot (Fig. 7) shows the distribution of the GMCI for each German state, ordered left-to-right from the lowest to highest median. The dashed horizontal line marks the national median (~ 0.46) for reference. States with clearly lower national values include Sachsen-Anhalt (~ 0.38) and Berlin (~ 0.39), followed by Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, Thüringen, Brandenburg and Sachsen (~ 0.43). Around the national level are Bremen, Hamburg, Nordrhein-Westfalen, Hessen and Niedersachsen (~ 0.45 – 0.47). Higher median values occur in Schleswig-Holstein, Rheinland-Pfalz, Bayern, Saarland, and Baden-Württemberg (~ 0.50 – 0.54). Lower tails in several eastern and northern states drop below 0.30, while upper tails in western and southern states extend to ~ 0.65 – 0.70 . Wider interquartile ranges and longer whiskers in some states reflect greater within-state variability.

Fig. 7. Green-Cool-Moist Index (GMCI) of the Federal States of Germany. The GMCI integrates land surface temperature (LST), September NDVI ($NDVI_{sep}$), and precipitation into a single 0–1 scale, with higher values indicating cooler, greener, and moister conditions.

4. Discussion

4.1. Green, moist, and cool as interdependent dimensions of ecosystem functionality

This study provides clear evidence that thermal regulation, vegetation cover, and moisture availability are strongly interlinked, supporting the concept of “green–moist–cool” as a fundamental ecological triad sustaining landscape functionality. Our mixed-effects models identified $NDVI_{sep}$ as the most important predictor of reduced land surface temperature (LST), exerting a far stronger cooling influence than precipitation and altitude. In turn, $NDVI_{sep}$ also emerged as the most consistent predictor of higher rainfall, reflecting its role in enhancing evapotranspiration, moisture recycling, and precipitation feedback. These results reinforce

recent theoretical and empirical studies that highlight the central role of vegetation in modulating local to regional climate (Adhikari et al., 2024; Miralles et al., 2025; Yuan et al., 2017).

The interdependence of greenness, moisture and cooling is not merely a correlation, but can be explained thermodynamically. Vegetation dissipates solar energy through evapotranspiration, reducing surface heating while moistening the atmosphere and facilitating further rainfall. As Makarieva et al. (2025) argue, plant transpiration should be viewed not as a “waste” of soil water but as an investment that amplifies atmospheric moisture import and enhances precipitation potential. Our results from Germany corroborate this principle: greener and cooler landscapes also consistently received more precipitation, while biomass-poor and hotter landscapes were comparatively drier.

Although (annual) precipitation and moisture are not synonymous, precipitation was included in our analysis as the available proxy for water input. It provides the necessary baseline of water supply against which vegetation functions. We recognize that the seasonal distribution of precipitation also plays a role, although its significance varies between open land and forests. For example, trees with deeper roots can also use water from winter precipitation in summer (Allen et al., 2019; Floriancic et al., 2024; Goldsmith et al., 2022).

Our results show that $NDVI_{sep}$ consistently outperformed precipitation in predicting cooling, underscoring that rainfall alone does not ensure ecological moisture. Rather, it is vegetation that determines whether precipitation is effectively retained, recycled, and translated into cooler and more resilient landscapes. This process reflects the role of *green water*—the portion of rainfall that infiltrates the soil and is used directly by plants to fuel photosynthesis, growth, and evapotranspiration-driven cooling (Feger & Hawtree, 2013; Rockström & Karlberg, 2010; te Wierik et al., 2020; Wang-Erlandsson et al., 2022). It has been suggested to include green water as a dimension in the planetary boundaries, which would help to capture the full scope of human impacts on the water cycle and ecosystem functioning (Wang-Erlandsson et al., 2022). This is relevant on a global scale and must also be applicable at a national level. Our results indicate that the concept of green water needs urgent attention, even in countries with a 'temperate' climate, such as Germany.

Including precipitation in the models highlights the contrast between mere water input and vegetation-driven moisture functionality. Degraded or sparsely vegetated regions enter a cycle

of dysfunction: reduced vegetation lowers evapotranspiration, which increases LST, suppresses rainfall, and further inhibits vegetation recovery. Such feedbacks are well-documented in arid and semi-arid regions (Abera et al., 2018; Olmos-Trujillo et al., 2020) but are now increasingly evident in temperate regions, like Germany, under climate change. The persistence of thermal hotspots such as the Maifeld–Neuwieder Becken or Oderbruch illustrates how land-use intensification can shift landscapes toward lower-functioning states, reducing the capacity to buffer heat and retain water.

Derived and used for the first time, the GMCI is a high-resolution monitoring tool to quantify landscape working capacity based on the green-moist-cool triad, integrating vegetation greenness, precipitation input and thermal regulation into a single dimensionless indicator. The GMCI map shows a clear divide in Germany's landscape functioning. High GMCI values cluster in forest areas where dense canopy, cooler LST, and higher rainfall coincide. Low GMCI values form broad belts across the eastern lowlands and peri-urban/agro-industrial basins. This spatial pattern implicates land-use intensity as the principal, management-controllable lever for restoring landscape working capacity. Computed at the pixel level yet aggregable to administrative or biophysical units, the GMCI resolves fine-scale heterogeneity while remaining directly interpretable. It offers a practical basis to prioritize landscape planning (e.g., silviculture, urban greening, irrigation management), to track annual trends in ecosystem working capacity, and to evaluate the performance of restoration and climate-adaptation measures.

4.2. Thermal landscape “pollution” and the overlooked role of rural heat regions

Much public and scientific debate on thermal extremes has focused on urban heat islands, where built surfaces and limited vegetation exacerbate health risks (Heaviside et al., 2017; Li et al., 2011; Liao et al., 2025; Phelan et al., 2015; Syrbe et al., 2024). Our findings confirm these patterns in urban hotspots such as Berlin, München or Köln, but they also reveal that thermal stress is not confined to cities. Agricultural lowlands with sparse canopy cover consistently exhibited LST values approaching or even matching those of urban areas, frequently exceeding 30 °C on hot days. Similar patterns have been reported in other regions where intensive agriculture contributes to elevated surface temperatures comparable to cities (Lai et al., 2020; Portela et al., 2020; Rangel-Peraza et al., 2024). These findings highlight that extensive rural heat landscapes, driven by large-scale land clearing and intensive cultivation, constitute a form of thermal landscape pollution. Such patterns demonstrate how unsustainable

land use amplifies the effects of climate change beyond city boundaries, exposing wide regions and their communities to elevated thermal risks. The embedding of urban centers within degraded rural heat regions compounds these risks. For example, Berlin lies within the Teltow–Berlin–Barnim heat region and surrounding lowland basins, which themselves are thermally stressed. Here, the urban heat island effect is not isolated but reinforced by surrounding agricultural plains, producing synergistic amplification of heat exposure. This highlights the importance of shifting the isolated policy discourse on urban heat islands to broader landscape systems. Rural landscapes, when degraded, multiply climate risks for both ecosystems and human populations (Yang et al., 2024).

Forested and wetland regions, by contrast, act as ‘climate infrastructure’. Their cooling capacity is not an ancillary ecosystem service but a core biophysical function derived from their ability to capture, transform, and store energy and water (Ellison et al., 2017; Gohr et al., 2021; Hesslerová et al., 2019). Forested uplands such as the Schwarzwald or Bayerischer Wald can be considered “climate refugia”, as they provide regional cooling and hydrological stability, but also as habitats for species adapted to cooler conditions. They are ‘slow lanes’ for species and essential components of climate adaptation strategies for the conservation of biodiversity under anthropogenic climate change, acting as temporary or long-term havens where species and ecosystems can persist (Morelli et al., 2020). Yet even within these cooler regions, our results show variation: the Schwarzwald recorded slightly higher LST on hot days than the Bavarian Forest or the Alps, a reminder that land-use intensity and exposure (e.g., valley agriculture, forestry practices, tourism infrastructure) can partly erode the natural cooling advantage of elevation and forest cover. Adhikari et al. (2024), Gohr et al. (2021) and Mildrexler et al. (2011) also show that although forests generally cool relative to other land covers. This effect can vary within forested regions depending on forest type and patch size, as well as land-use intensity and the characteristics of the surrounding landscape matrix (Mann et al. 2023; Adhikari et al. (2024).

4.3. Working landscapes as thermodynamic systems

Ecosystems have been identified as a system of dynamic equilibrium, whereby they perpetually seek to maximize the storage of free energy. This has been shown to result in an increased capacity to utilize and dissipate available energy, leading to a greater deviation from thermodynamic equilibrium (Jørgensen et al., 2000). The idea of using exergy in ecology is often explained as a way of applying the Darwinian idea of "survival of the fittest" to

thermodynamics: the ecosystem that is best able to use and store energy and materials in the most efficient way would be the fittest (Nielsen et al., 2020). Recent studies use energy and entropy fluxes to estimate the "work efficiency" of ecosystems, defined as the work performed relative to incoming radiation. This allows for cross-ecosystem comparisons and links ecosystem structure to thermodynamic advantage. Calculating thermodynamic efficiency at the ecosystem level is more complex than for engineered systems due to open boundaries, multiple energy forms, and biological diversity. Some methods require extensive data on energy flows, material exchanges, and system structure, which can be challenging to obtain (Nielsen et al., 2020; Nielsen & Müller, 2023). Our proxies for work capacities are a relatively simple and spatially explicit approximation; future work should calibrate them against formal thermodynamic metrics (e.g., exergy, emergy, entropy production, and radiative work efficiency) to establish their validity, sensitivity, and scope of application.

Urban areas and intensively cultivated lowlands, for example Oderbruch or Maifeld–Neuwieder Becken, exhibit reduced greenness, elevated LST, and suppressed rainfall, reflecting diminished work capacity. The thermodynamic role of ecosystems is not merely theoretical but observable at landscape scale: functional vegetation actively dissipates solar energy through evapotranspiration, sustains hydrological cycles, and stores carbon and water (Hayden, 1998; Huryňa & Pokorný, 2016; Makarieva et al., 2025; Miralles et al., 2025).

Our findings have direct implications for restoration and land-use planning. Reforestation, greening, and wetland restoration increase vegetation cover, which enhances energy capture (via photosynthesis), carbon sequestration, and nutrient cycling. They also improve landscape connectivity and thermal buffering, stabilizing local microclimates and increasing the system's ability to dissipate energy gradients—key aspects of thermodynamic work capacity. With this perspective, adaptation strategies are not only about conserving biodiversity or sequestering carbon, but also about strengthening the fundamental thermodynamic functions of ecosystems that reinforce socioecological resilience under climate change.

4.4. Implications for climate adaptation and ecosystem restoration

The climate crisis will worsen within a short timeframe. According to climate research, Europe should prepare for events of a similar intensity to the 2018–2020 compound event, but with durations exceeding anything experienced in the last 250 years (Rakovec et al., 2022). It is now essential that the climate-regulating functions of ecosystems are preserved as far as possible or

significantly developed. The landscape ranking derived from our analysis provides a practical framework for identifying both crisis regions and ecological strongholds in Germany. Equally critical is the capacity to rank and prioritize areas based on their vulnerability so that management efforts and conservation resources can be directed where they will have the greatest impact.

At the upper end of the ranking, forested uplands and alpine ecosystems emerge as high-capacity ecological powerhouses. Their ability to buffer heat extremes is reinforced by altitude and greater rainfall, partly driven by orographic precipitation. Yet their capacity is not absolute, and orography alone does not guarantee resilience. The extent of cooling and moistening strongly depends on intact vegetation structure and low land-use intensity, which sustain evapotranspiration, canopy shading, and hydrological cycling (Albrich et al., 2020). Recent forest dieback (Enderle et al., 2018; Frei et al., 2022; Knutzen et al., 2025; Spiecker & Kahle, 2023; Winter et al., 2025) illustrates how drought and other climate stressors, interacting with land-use intensity, can undermine these cooling and moistening capacities.

Landscapes with diminished ecological working capacity require restoration, while those with high capacity must be maintained, both relying on effective management to secure the ecosystem services for regional and national climate resilience. Our results further suggest that natural climate protection should begin at fine spatial scales, where vegetation functions as active infrastructure regulating energy and water balances.

There is currently an increasingly intense debate about where measures to implement the EU Nature Restoration Law (European Union, 2024) should primarily be taken, whether in European protected areas (Natura 2000) or outside them. For some stakeholders, the conservation status of the various habitat types may play a role in this debate. We strongly recommend a function-oriented approach that takes into account the values of the green-wet-cool index. Spatial priorities can be identified at national level and within the federal states but also at local level.

4.5. Societal importance and socioecological resilience

Improving the thermodynamic functions of ecosystems enhances their socioecological resilience by providing a greater range of ecosystem services. Cooler, moister landscapes offer rural communities reduced heat stress and provide a mitigation effect against urban heat islands (Yang et al., 2024), thereby lowering health risks during periods of extreme temperatures for

society as a whole. Furthermore, improved water retention supports agriculture, secures drinking water supplies and mitigates flood risks. At the same time, enhanced vegetation cover stabilizes crop yields, strengthens local economies and improves social well-being (Ellison et al., 2024; Gohr et al., 2021; Jackson et al., 2008). Conversely, degraded heat landscapes risk cascading failures, including reduced crop productivity, tree dieback, loss of carbon sinks and increased runoff leading to flooding. Thus, the complex interdependencies between social outcomes and the working landscapes improve socioecological resilience, highlighting the importance of considering all ecosystem services in policy and landscape planning.

Recognizing these interdependencies is crucial in addressing the climate crisis. As Makarieva et al. (2023) emphasized, the global climatic role of natural forests is underestimated in current projections and policies. Building on this, our results show that sustaining green–moist–cool conditions is essential not only for local adaptation, but also for maintaining regional and continental climate stability in temperate working landscapes.

4.6. Policy and management roadmap

The World Bank's message in its recent report "Reboot development" is clear: 'Development cannot succeed on a damaged planet, and policies cannot succeed without considering the whole system. Environmental reforms that ignore how land, water, air, and people interact often backfire' (Damania et al., 2025). Our findings emphasize that addressing thermal landscapes in Germany is not only a matter of climate change adaptation but an urgent task of reducing harm caused by inappropriate land use that multiplies climate impacts and risks for people and economy. The recognition that green, moist, and cool conditions reflect the physical work of ecosystems provides a practical and measurable framework for evaluating environmental suitability and prioritizing action. Based on our results, several policy directions emerge:

National monitoring of ecosystem functionality and work capacity

- Create a national inventory of ecosystem functionality. The results of such an inventory should be incorporated into land use planning, settlement planning and disaster management, and should guide restoration measures in such a way that they also provide the greatest possible benefit for biodiversity conservation and natural climate protection. Focusing on green, wet and cool areas is particularly synergistic in this regard. Monitoring positive and negative changes and quantifying the

resulting creation of value and damage can be used to create land use management tools (e.g., subsidy programs for natural climate protection).

- Establish a national monitoring system. Use new metrics for comparative assessments. Understanding ecosystems as power stations that capture and convert solar energy, thereby performing landscape work and regulatory functions, represents a new way of looking at nature and implies the need for monitoring frameworks that move beyond static land-use maps. Regular, annual assessment of LST, NDVI, and precipitation via remote sensing would allow identification and prioritization of both functional ecosystems and crisis landscapes.
- Reporting and new indicators should be institutionalized. Available data should inform regular national reports, providing a new perspective on Germany's ecosystems and their productive capacity. This endeavor must be recognized as fundamental to economic development, livelihoods, and human wellbeing, not merely as relevant to nature conservation.
- Based on a system of functional indicators, such as the GMCI, a national 'gross natural product' should be developed and assessed regularly – the totality of all work performed by nature or the functionality of Germany's ecosystems. This is not about monetizing ecosystem services, but rather establishing a basic benchmark for assessing 'natural wealth', which can also be used to measure sustainable development. This would facilitate the recognition of ecosystem functionality as a key condition for economic activities, acknowledging the vital contribution of ecosystems to national security and prosperity.

Actively manage the 'temperature landscape'

- Prioritize rural heat regions for action as much as urban green areas.
- Cool agricultural landscapes through structural diversification. Measures such as agroforestry, hedgerows, and mosaic landscapes with three-dimensional biomass can reduce heat loads, protect soils, and improve water retention, while delivering co-benefits for humus formation, carbon sequestration and biodiversity.
- Recognize micro- and meso-climate protection and establish programs for the protection of climate refugia.

This manuscript has been submitted to [Earth's Future](#) for consideration.

- Address risks of low-functioning “crisis landscapes.” Without intervention, these areas risk cascading failures: reduced agricultural productivity, tree dieback, poorer drinking water supply, loss of carbon sinks, and increased runoff.
- Start an ethical discussion about how heat and drought affect biodiversity and species protection. When humans suffer from heat, other organisms do too. Further research should be conducted to identify indicators that can be used to measure heat and drought stress experienced by other creatures. For the sake of ecosystem function, we need cooler climate refugia all over our landscapes, but we also need them to safeguard the existence of viable populations of as many species as possible and to reduce the suffering of our co-habitants in our territories, which, among others, is an imperative of animal protection.

Define natural climate protection better

- Assessments of human interventions in the landscape and the use of plant biomass must be reevaluated in terms of their climate impact. The protection of cooler and buffered local climates, translates into natural climate protection by stabilizing ecosystem carbon pools.
- Further studies should identify minimum sizes for cooling landscapes to function effectively, bearing in mind that such parameters can only ever be snapshots in a changing climate. This could help ensure that future land use approval procedures prevent the further fragmentation of reasonably intact ecosystems and create sufficiently large, functional ones (for example, through climate-friendly land consolidation). This analysis provides initial guidance on such considerations and thus assists in implementing recent political decisions on protecting and restoring ecosystems.
- The results of the study should inform the management and use of forests, an area in which climate protection is becoming an increasingly important consideration. If it is evident that biomass quantity, tree species composition and soil damage caused by machinery have a significant impact on ecosystem functioning in terms of cooling and precipitation, these findings should be incorporated into government funding guidelines and, better still, laws and regulations.
- The metric we propose can also help to identify priority areas or regions that should be restored under EU Restoration Law. In any case, we recommend using functional

parameters, as proposed in this study, to design and monitor restoration measures that also have a synergistic effect in terms of natural climate protection.

Acknowledgements

The research was funded and realized by ECONICS INSTITUTE. PLI acknowledges the research professorship granted by the Eberswalde University for Sustainable Development (EUSD). We would like to thank the Greenpeace Environmental Foundation, Germany (Umweltstiftung Greenpeace) for supporting PLI's professorship at EUSD as well as Ecosia GmbH, elobau Foundation and Graf Hermann von Hatzfeldt for supporting DJ's professorship at EUSD.

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Writing – original draft: YA, PLI

Writing – review & editing: all authors

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest for this manuscript.

Open Research (availability statement)

All source datasets and software used in this study are publicly accessible. The processed dataset associated with this study is available on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/17081072>

Softwares used:

Google Earth Engine (GEE): cloud-based geospatial processing platform (<https://earthengine.google.com>).

This manuscript has been submitted to [Earth's Future](#) for consideration.

QGIS 3.34: open-source geographic information system (<https://qgis.org>).
R version 4.3.3 and RStudio 2024.09: statistical computing environment (<https://cran.r-project.org>, <https://posit.co>).

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